

A Study on Women's Education in Tirunelveli District

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Abstract

Women's Education Is one of the biggest tools for 'effective development' of any country. It means freedom of women from the vicious circle of social, political, economic and gender-based discrimination. Making women aware of their rights and developing confidence in them – is a central issue. It is essential for them to be skilled in order to be able to better serve their families at home as well as professionally. Skill development not only creates employment opportunities but also empowers them. The aim of skill development, in case of women, is not just simply preparing them for jobs; but also to boost their performance by improving the quality of work in which they are involved. This paper clearly highlights the impact of skill development on women empowerment. The basic need for empowering women is to in still the required skills and abilities in order to shape up their overall personality & raise their status within the society.

Keywords: Women's Education, Skill Development, Inclusive Growth.

Introduction

The establishment of British rule in India marked the beginning of a new era in the history of political, economic, social and educational systems. Of all these, the educational system opened new vistas by creating a new set of opportunities in the society. As a result a new class of intelligentsia trained in modern Western Sciences and Cultures emerged in the Indian Society. This intelligentsia became the pioneers of all progressive democratic movements. Of all the activities carried out by this group, emancipation of Women is more significant. On one hand, the British liberal views, Christian missionary activities and the attitudes of the bureaucrats helped in judging the position of women in relation to the European standards and values that led to the condemnation of the customs and conventions of traditional Indian society relating to women such as child marriage, sati, dowry, illiteracy and widowhood. Due to their effort, sati, female infanticide and slavery were abolished. In addition to this, several other reforms were also introduced in relation to Government business and public works. Sunday has been made a day of rest, and the converts have been protected, by a special enactment enforced in Tirunelveli District by the Government of Madras and East India Company on 16.07.1805. This enactment legalized as a result of the enquiry report submitted by Mr. Lushington, the then Collector of Tirunelveli district. It also

paved the way for Grant-in-Aid system (regular annual grant to schools by the Government) and the Missionary schools were no longer excluded from the benefit of Government grants. On the other hand, westernization created an awareness regarding the subordinate position of women and the need for rationalizing and eliminating the traditional customs and conventions which were creeping into the society. The Britishers, Christian missionaries as well as the Western educated Indians felt that “educating women” is the only means through which the emancipation of Indian women can be achieved. Thus the importance of educating women was first published in Bengal by the Atmiya Sabha, founded by Raja Ram Mohan Roy in 1815. This led to the starting of a First Formal Female School at Nazareth by Rev. James Hough, the C.M.S. Missionary, in Tirunelveli District³ of Madras Presidency and in South India in 1820.

History of Tirunelveli

Tirunelveli is properly named as “Tirunelveli” purporting to mean the land surrounded by beautiful paddy fields. The Tirunelveli Sthalapurana prescribes a tradition for the origin of the Tirunelveli. One Vedararma, a staunch devotee of Lord Siva collected paddy by way of begging and carried on his ablutions in Tambraparni. One day he prayed to the Lord for rain. His prayer was answered and the Lord showered rain immediately. Vedararma witnessed a wonderful miracle that, the area spreading the paddy was under the sunlight. Since that day, the town was called Tirunelveli (Thiru + Nel+ Velli) which means “Sacred hedged paddy”. Other names of Tirunelveli are Venuvanam, Thirumoorthipuram, Ibapuri, Tharanisaram and Sakalasithi 6 Nellai, Nellaiyampathy or Nellaiyambalam.

Definition of Women’s Education

Women’s Education is termed as “Providing for all facilities and opportunities for the learning of females on par with those available for the education of males”.⁵³ Those Women belong to poverty line were not contribute directly to the economic development of the country. Therefore, the missionaries believed in the concept that if they educate a woman, they educate a family and society that would contribute directly to the economic development. Hence, they decided to educate the poor and middle class women by following anti – Downward Filtration Theory and succeed in their attempt in this regard. [Downward Filtration Theory in education was introduced by East India Company. It meant that coming down of knowledge from the higher class people to the lower classes].

Importance of Women’s Education

The progress of any nation interlinked with women’s education which plays an important role in the society. Without providing proper educational opportunities for all women in our country who constitute roughly about 50 percent of the population, it is futile to think of achieving universal literacy. Many of the social reformers like Swami Vivekananda, Subramanian Bharathiar, Mahatma Gandhi, Annie Beasant and Sarojini Naidu emphasized the need for women’s education.

Objectives of the Study

- The main objectives of the present study are as follows:
- To analyze the salient features of the women’s education in Tirunelveli district;
- To highlight the work of indigenous societies, missionaries on the one hand and the East India Company and Crown on the other hand towards the education of women in Tirunelveli district;

- To trace the origin and growth of women's education in Tirunelveli district during which covers more than one and a half century, that would help the research scholars to undertake further research in this field.
- To explain the historic development of primary education, higher education, industrial education and special education for women in Tirunelveli district; and
- To understand the history of formal female educational institutions, and its development during the 19th and the first half of the 20th century.

Hypotheses

This research titled "Women's Education in Tirunelveli District from traces the history of Tirunelveli District, development of Primary Education for Women, genesis of Higher Education for Women, development of Industrial Education for Women, origin and development of Special Education.

Review of Literature

Scholars like M.Sargur Doss, Educational Policy in Madras Presidency 1800-1900, (Unpublished Ph.D. Thesis, University of Madras (Madras,1961), and Lalitha Jayaraman, History of Education in Madras Presidency 1800-1857 (Unpublished M.Phil. Dissertation, University of Madras, 1986) in their research analyzed the British Educational System in Madras Presidency; Anlet Sobitha Bai.W., in her Dissertation titled Contribution of Protestant Women Missionaries in Tirunelveli (1823-1924),(Unpublished M.Phil., Dessertation, M.S. University, Tirunelveli) dealt the contribution of Women Protestant Missionaries in Tirunelveli between 1823 to 1924; and, Anjaline Bama.S., in her Dissertation titled Nellai Maavattaththil Kalvi Vallarchip - paniyil Selvi. Anne Jane Askwith Ammaiyaarin Tondur (Tamil), (Unpublished M.Phil Dessertation, M.S. University, April,1995) enumerate the contributions of Miss. Anne Jane Askwith towards Education in Tirunelveli.

Scope of the Study

During the ancient period, men and women received the same type of education and enjoyed the same status. The curriculum was religious in nature and they learnt together in the same place. In the medieval period, the practice of child marriage and purdah system resulted in the decline of women's education. After the advent of the British in India, women's education was promoted by the Christian Missionaries and by the British government. There were various studies which throw light on the development of English education and the policies followed by the British towards this cause. The provision of English education represents the most sustained and far-reaching attempts of a society to create consciousness among certain sections of that society like backward castes and women. So, educational system plays a greater importance in any society. To understand the regional variations in the growth of education, the regional and district level research on history of education is necessary to know the complete history of education in India. Therefore the researcher has analyzed that the history of women's education in India in the nineteenth and twentieth century's.

Sources

This study is based on the archival materials such as the Proceedings of Board of Revenue, Public Consultations, Tirunelveli District Records, Selections from the Educational Records, Reports of the Indian Education Commission, Annual Reports on the Public Instruction in the Madras Presidency, District Gazetteers and Manuals, Educational Reports of Missionaries in India,

the Report of the Primary Education Committee (1929-30), the Sargeant Committee Report (1944), and the Hansa Mehta Report on the Post-war Educational Reconstruction with special reference to women's education (1945), Quinquennial Reports on Education. The secondary sources include books, articles, journals and newspapers. Personal interviews with the members of the Diocese of Palayamcottai, Diocese of Tirunelveli, Stephen Neil Research Centre, Thembavani Thottam Roman Catholic Centre, St. Xavier College, St. John's College, and Tirunelveli Social Service Centre, Palamcottah, interviews with the people at Melapalayam, Kollimalai, Sankaranainarkoil, Thoothukudi, Vadamalapuram, Moovirndazhi, Achampatti, Devarkulam, Palayapettai, Sivalaperi have been carried out to obtain first hand information and data relating to the study.

Research Methodology

The methodology adopted in the presentation of this study is historical, analytical and exploratory. The researcher visited the institutions in person to collect first hand information. Attempts were made to interview the past and present faculty members, educated people in villages and questionnaires were distributed to find the system of education, curriculum, the historic reason for the genesis of Female School, Teacher Training Institutions, Female High Schools, First Women's College, Vocational Training Centers, and the First Special School in Tirunelveli District of Madras Presidency.

Limitations

- The period of study is limited from Tirunelveli District.
- Origin, growth and development of women's education only in Tirunelveli District.
- The primary education, higher education, industrial education and special education for women in this district alone have been dealt in this study.
- This research does not analyze the entire educational policies of Madras Presidency and India.

Suggestions

It is found that personal core factors affect teachers' job satisfaction more than work corefactors. Therefore; institutions must launch solutions for teachers' personal problems. Encouragement system for rewarding successful teachers in schools should be developed. In schools individual goal notion is much more important than collective goal, institutions following team works which create collective habits such as "team spirit" and "we concept" is a good step towards eliminating one of the fundamental factors of teachers dissatisfaction. For increasing employees' job satisfaction and institutions effectiveness, it will be useful to provide "individual consulting services" to teachers in the schools. Another tip for increasing teachers' job satisfaction might be developing projects that create the notion of "social responsibility" instead of "commerce quotient". Formulation of a fair promotion system will increase employees' motivation and their jobsatisfaction. Another way of increasing employees' job satisfaction might be developing educational activities for personnel improvement. State Governments must ensure the local policy infrastructure envisaged in the Education Sector for Reforms and District Devolution Plan to become real. Inclusion of teachers in decision-making is important for bottom up communication of priorities and needs. This can be done through the establishment of an independent professional body of teachers. They should encourage greater teacher involvement in policy-making for schools they manage or support.

Conclusion

Education is the most important means of empowering women with the knowledge, skills and self-confidence necessary to participate fully in the development process. Given a fair opportunity

in education, women can significantly lift a nation out of difficulty and hardship through their important societal roles. In ancient India, the traditions of society and the nation were preserved in schools. Rig Veda says that education is something which makes man self-reliant and selfless; Upanishad mentioned that education is for liberation. Man's ego has generally adopted a biased view of the education of women. It is because of this that the nature of feminine education differs from that of masculine education. Consequently, girls were educated at home, despite which the name of such woman scholar Andal, who composed Tiruppavai Tiruvenba belongs to Srivilliputtur in Tirunelveli District. The place assigned to women in the educational system of ancient periods was very limited and restricted. This study reveals that in the pyal schools, low caste people as well as girls were not admitted. Education of a Muslim child would start on a particular day. There was, besides, a school of the domestic type. Although women's education was restricted due to purdah system, yet there is no doubt that young girls were taught in the schools. Girls of higher classes received education in their own houses from learned ladies or old men who served as private tutors. Women's education was hampered because of the practice of child marriage which was widely prevalent both in the Hindu and Muslim families. On the whole during the medieval period, education of women was not significant.

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